

THE ROLE OF PARALLEL CORPUS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article deals with the corpus and its significance, types of corpus, parallel corpus of Uzbek scientific texts, a new type of linguistic sources and the problems of creating parallel corpus of texts.

Key words: computer linguistics, corpus linguistics, Brown Corpus, parallel corpus, source language, translation language, parallel corpus of scientific texts.

INTRODUCTION

At a time when time is rapidly developing, changes in the social, political, economic and cultural spheres of the world are first of all little reflected in the language. Every people, nation tries to preserve, develop and introduce its language to the world. Preservation of languages means preservation of national culture. The development of computer technologies at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century and the wide spread of the Internet laid the groundwork for the emergence of the fields of computer linguistics and corpus linguistics of modern linguistics. In the first half of the 90s of the 20th century, corpus linguistics was formed as a separate part of the science of language. The years in the usage of linguistic corpus made it much easier for the linguists to learn the presence of observation, sample and evidence collection, comparison, and conclusions facilitated this study. Convenient interface and search engine in the language corpus serves as an object of research. The proof of the grammatical interpretation of the speech of the linguists was no longer a novelty for the age of corpus linguistics. Typical cases, examples of ten, hundred, and thousands of examples in the corpus studies help the researcher to conclude; unusual situations also create new theoretical views. In other words, new discoveries in the speech, new combinations and structures allow for new hypotheses in linguistics.

The term "*adapted*" refers to the translation units in the corpus means that there is a clear connection to the carrier, and it is precisely this type of housing that is preferred have A parallel text corpus is a relatively new type of linguistic resources. This type the first sources appeared in the late 1980s - early 1990s.

Several related parallel text corpora in the last decade projects have been launched. When creating parallel corpora of texts, one language and unlike comparative texts, considering the factor of intercultural relations need to get Source language (MT) texts are only translated into second language (TT) are texts. Thus, if there is no cross-cultural communication at all, PKM it is impossible to create a parallel between the states according to the level of different relations there is a need for a corps. A parallel corpus, like two linguistics is the intersection of culture. In general, a researcher in the composition of PKM the following language resources may be available:

- ❖ special texts;
- ❖ public media texts;
- ❖ scientific texts;
- ❖ artistic texts.

A parallel corpus is a parallel electronic analogue of translated texts mainly consists of bilingual translation texts. In the case that electronic texts are the original text itself or a part of it can. Several scientists, including D. Dobrovolsky, Yu. Tao, V. Zakharov, A. Kokoreva and E. Sosnina, talk about the structure, composition and capabilities of the parallel body especially recognized in their research work.¹

Parallel regarding the improvement of actions performed in the corpus many scientists have conducted scientific research. Among these scientists, Key and according to Roscheisen, in translation, the sentences fit together for, first of all, it is important to achieve the alternation of words but it is not easy to achieve the alternation of text words in two languages and this alternative may not be adequate.²

If several texts of the searched word in the parallel corpus the learning process of research through the provision of meanings. Similar to Word fast in the process of segmentation and linguistic analysis for parallel text instruments are an effective technological tool. Based on corpus material, which words are always by statistical method as a result, it is related to a stable combination can be determined. These textbooks have an exercise suite for identifying original and translated language equivalents. The main task of this assignment is to analyze the lexical and grammatical structure of the parallel context. The student is given original and translation (several variants of translation):

- ❖ the source of the review and analysis will be clear;
- ❖ it is only for the students to analyze and synthesize, to make linguistics summaries, to bring the conclusions to the translation skills.

In parallel, the parallel corpus provides the advantage of other learning resources as the source of particular resources. In fact, it is desirable for the translation to be carried out with reference to the next editing.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that any language must find its place in order to be preserved in society and especially in the development of world science, and the role of the parallel corpus is extremely important in this. The corpus helps to make research in any field of linguistics qualitative and effective. When creating a parallel corpus of scientific texts, it is necessary to take into account the factor of intercultural relations. It should be noted that the corpus-based approach to modern translation education creates new opportunities. In contrast to the National Corpus, this body provides a basis for the study of translation features in a specific field based on massive material.

Creating parallel frameworks for scientific, technical, socio-political, economical and other fields allows for a special study of language skills in this area. Today in the world of computer linguistics there are a number of concomitant programs, corpus managers, and a small (parallel and comparative) corpus with special goals. For the Uzbek language such contradictions and corpus managers' development are the most important tasks facing the computer linguistic expert today.

¹Кокорева А.А. Корпус параллельных текстов в обучении иностранному языку. — Вестник ТГУ (Тамбовский государственный университет), выпуск 2 (118), 2013. — С. 57– 62.

²Resnik P. Parallel Strands: A Preliminary Investigation into Mining the Web for Bilingual Text, Proceedings of the Conference of the Association for Machine Translation in the Americas (AMTA-98), — Langhorne, PA, 1998. — URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/3-540-49478-2_7

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